

MEMORIES

Memory
My companion
Conveys
My joy and pain.
It knows well
What with am I attached,
Silently it dwells
As if totally detached.

Hopes
Though keep fading
Illusions
Though keep moving;
Searching peace
Searching for new hopes,
I find, there's no grace
In vain, I opt to stop.

Nature
I loved utmost
The roses
I cherished most,
Lovely birds
I pleasantly watched,
They often reflect
On memories screen.

ENLIGHTENMENT

The fickle mind
Cannot give up
Its thirst for wealth,
It's thirst for luxuries,
It's thirst for supremacy,
It's thirst for autocracy;
Yes, it cannot give up
Unless inwardly ...
It gets enlightened.

Kindled by desires fire
Unable to douse the ire
Heart feels encircled,
Heart feels entangled,
Feels complete isolation
With pricking emotion.
The fluctuating mind
With the worldly bonds
Can it get enlightened?

BRIEF BIO :

Dr. Ashok Chakravarthy Tholana is a writer, poet and reviewer, hailing from Hyderabad City, Telangana State, INDIA, whose message-oriented poems achieved a rare distinction of getting published in no less than a hundred countries. His message-centric poems on Universal Peace, World Brotherhood, Environment Consciousness, Protection of Nature, Safeguarding Children's and Human Rights have been translated to 41 languages as of now.

Dr. Ashok is conferred with several prestigious national and international awards that include Fourteen Doctorates, numerous citations, commendations, titles etc.

For his humane approach through poetry writings, he received applause from Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam, former-President, India, Shri Atal Behari Vajpayee, former-Prime Minister, India, Bill Clinton, USA, Queen Elizabeth of Britain, Princess of Wales, President and Prime Minister of France, Prime Minister of Switzerland, Senator Viktor Busa, The Lord President, Italy, United Nations Organization, UNESCO, UNICEF etc.

ELEVEN Poetry Books have been Published so far, viz. (1) CHARISMATA OF POESIE (2) THE CHARIOT OF MUSINGS (3) SERENE THOUGHTS (4) TWINKLES (5) REFLECTIONS (6) ALTITUDES (7) OUTLET (8) HORIZON (9) KALEIDOSCOPE (10) VIBRANT MUSINGS (11) YOURS POETICALLY. That apart, Ashok has translated 13 spiritual books and 4 other books from local Telugu to English language.

PROMOTING UNIVERSAL PEACE: For the past TWO decades, Dr. Ashok is making relentless efforts through poetry contributions for promoting Global Peace through the concept of non-violence, supporting Anti-Nuclear Manifesto, protecting Environment, protecting Children Rights etc. As a Co-author, his contributions are acknowledged @:

- **Global Peace Science of Spherons:** <https://peacefromharmony.org/docs/global-peace-science-2016.pdf>
- **Gandhica:** https://peacefromharmony.org/?cat=en_c&key=848
- **Anti-Nuclear Manifesto:** https://peacefromharmony.org/?cat=en_c&key=908
- **International Day of Nonviolence- October 2** -https://peacefromharmony.org/?cat=en_c&key=1158

Promoting Environment and Peace through videos

- **2025 UNOs World Environment Day @::**
https://youtu.be/t_vsArHn-U0?si=YPxN8sJ_fEDcA0Xz?sub_confirmation=1
- **2025 UNOs International Day of Peace @ ::**
https://youtu.be/GI_eTFEyweQ?si=1e6zdT-TyZvZ-3kv?sub_confirmation=1